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EVALUATIVE ANTHROPONYMS AS ELEMENTS OF ENGLISH ONOMASTIC WORLDVIEW*

The present article addresses the analysis of the semantic peculiarities of English evaluative anthroponyms, the latter being viewed as onomastic worldview elements. By the evaluative anthroponym we mean a person's name (first name, last name and nickname) the semantics of which contains an evaluative component.

The research corpus has been compiled in compliance with the criteria of language material selection. The methodology of the study is based on the combination of traditional, axiological and linguacultural approaches, which enables us to identify the specific features of the English onomastic worldview, the system of ethno-cultural values, language and culture dominants.

The research material has been classified into eight classes according to the semantic principles.

Key words: *evaluation, connotation, anthroponym, semantic class, structural type, word-building model.*

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ОЦЕНОЧНЫЕ АНТРОПОНИМЫ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА

В настоящей статье приводятся результаты анализа семантических особенностей английских оценочных антропонимов, которые рассматриваются как элементы ономастической картины мира. Под оценочным антропонимом мы понимаем имя человека (имя, фамилию и прозвище), семантика которого содержит оценочный компонент.

Корпус исследования был составлен в соответствии с критериями отбора языкового материала. Методология исследования основана на сочетании традиционного, аксиологического и лингвокультурологического подходов, что позволяет выявить специфические особенности английской ономастической картины мира, описать систему этнокультурных ценностей и доминант английского языка и культуры.

В результате семантической классификации было выделено восемь групп оценочных антропонимов.

Ключевые слова: *оценка, коннотация, антропоним, семантический класс, структурный тип, словообразовательная модель.*

1. Introduction

Our ancestors believed in the connection between a person's name, fate and character. Knowing someone's name (a kind of sociolinguistic code) meant having power over this person. In ancient Sumer, the etymology of the word *fate* was associated with the verb *to name*. An anthroponymic stem can elucidate intentions of parents, their hopes and thoughts in the process of naming. In any linguistic community, personal names can cause positive or negative associations, but in each individual linguaculture the set of factors influencing the emergence of

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additional connotations in anthroponymic semantics is different.

The present research focuses on semantic and linguacultural features of English personal names (anthroponyms) with an evaluative component in their semantic structure. This paper aims at shedding some new light on the linguacultural analysis of evaluative anthroponymic semantics in English.

An evaluative anthroponym (hereinafter EA) is defined as a person's name (personal name, surname and nickname), the lexical background of which contains an evaluative component [Сысоева, 2016: 16]. Evaluation is a connotation component in anthroponymic meaning, which can be explicated on the basis of the following set of name characteristics:

- native – foreign (borrowed);
- rarely used – frequently used;
- active – passive;
- familiar – unfamiliar;
- associated with positive-evaluative – negative-evaluative vocabulary units;
- identical to names of worthy – unworthy known name-bearers.

In the present study, we develop the approach to the analysis of evaluation within anthroponymic connotative meaning suggested by Ye. Volf [Вольф, 2024] and N. Arutyunova [Арутюнова, 1988]. Evaluation in semantic structure of anthroponymic lexis is considered as a unity of the following elements:

- the subject of the evaluation (the one who gives the name),
- the object of the evaluation (the one who is given the name),
- the type of the evaluation (absolute positive or negative evaluation),
- the basis of the evaluation (factors determining positive or negative evaluation mark in an anthroponym).

Here are the most salient semantic features of anthroponyms: native – foreign or borrowed, active – passive, familiar – unfamiliar. The feature familiar – unfamiliar makes it possible to determine the etymology which, in turn, is closely related to the cultural component of connotation, and to state that the name has a pronounced national identity, i.e. such a name has chances to be used in the patriotic family. The features frequently used – rarely used and familiar – unfamiliar enables the naming participants to realize their preferences as far as the name giving frequency is concerned. These features reveal the system of values and naming preferences in the English linguaculture.

2. Materials and Methods

In modern onomastic studies, a significant interest is attached to anthroponyms, which is accounted for by the anthropocentric paradigm development in linguistics.

The problem of connotative meaning formation within anthroponymic semantics has repeatedly been researched into by prominent onomatologists and lexicologists [Отин, 2004; Лукаш, 2011].

The problem of connotative onyms (connotonyms, the term suggested by Ye. Otin) was separately considered in the system of more general issues: problems of nomination in onomastics [Суперанская, 2023; Ермолович, 2001].

Although the proper names specificity is already largely understood, the study of evaluative anthroponyms as units of English onomastic worldview, a system of knowledge about the nation formed on the basis of proper names, make up an innovative direction in present-day anthroponymics.

3275 evaluative anthroponyms selected from the anthroponymic dictionaries Oxford Dictionary of First Names [Hanks & Hodges, 2006], The Wordsworth Dictionary of First Names [Freedman, 1997], Oxford Dictionary of Nicknames [Delahunty, 2003], Dictionary of English Personal Names [Рыбакин, 2000] make up the research corpus. The language material was further verified and elaborated according to the online resources: Collins English Dictionary and Thesaurus, and Behind the name. The choice of the above sources enables us to study the axiological evolution in names' semantics and changes in naming preferences over time.

The purpose, objectives and material informed the research methods employed. The method of component analysis was used to establish the semantic volume of evaluative anthroponyms, integral and differential features of their lexical meaning. The etymological method made it possible to identify the origin of appellative stems in evaluative anthroponyms. With the help of the linguacultural analysis, ethnolinguistic features of evaluative anthroponyms as specific linguistic units reflecting the attitude of native speakers to certain fragments of reality were traced. The use of quantitative method provided ground for establishing the productivity of units entering different semantic types, as well as the ways of the English anthroponymic system enrichment.

3. Theoretical background

The category of evaluation is universal, since there is no language that lacks the notion of good or bad. As V. Vinogradov notes, «the word not only possesses grammatical, lexical and objective meanings, but at the same time expresses the evaluation of the subject ...» [Виноградов, 1977: 24]. In our opinion, this definition universally describes semantic features of anthroponyms in different languages.

Evaluation can be studied in two dimensions: as a category of logic and as a linguistic category. In logic, evaluation is defined as a value judgment. To evaluate is to express a thought, reasoning about the value or significance of someone or something. The main sphere of meanings, which are traditionally correlated with evaluative ones, is associated with the signs good – bad. The category of evaluation is also associated with the predicates «good» and «bad» in linguistics [Бессонова, 2002: 12].

3.1. In this research, evaluative meaning is understood as «information about a positive or negative attitude of a speech participant towards a particular property of the object discussed» [Телия, 1986: 98]. Evaluative semantics can be categorised according to various criteria; however, the primary domain of evaluative meanings is grounded in the opposition good and bad.

One of the elements of the evaluation structure is the axiological scale, which can be represented in the form of various models. In the present study, we adopted the axiological model developed by N. Arutyunova [Арутюнова, 1988], O. Bessonova [Бессонова, 2003; Bessonova, 2018], Ye. Volf [Вольф, 2024], A. Wierzbicka [Вежбицкая, 1996]. According to this model, the evaluation norm is not contained in the middle of the scale but coincides with its positive edge. Thus, the norm acquires an axiological function and is perceived as something normal, which means positive, while lexical units with the meaning ‘deviation from the norm’ are perceived as negative. For example, the name *Rhonwen (f)*, derived from the appellatives *rhawn* ‘hair’ and *gwen* ‘white’, is popular in Wales. The persistent popularity of this anthroponym is due to its association with the name of the lyrical heroine of Welsh medieval poetry, who the authors praised as the standard of national beauty [Behind the Name]. That is, *fair hair* is perceived as a norm, thus endowing the name with positive evaluation.

Some linguists come to the conclusion that the quantitative advantage of negative evaluation lexis is also associated with the idea of a norm. Normally, a person does not focus on events or situations when he / she feels good. But when someone feels bad (deviation from the norm occurs), he / she uses a number of ways to communicate about it. Obviously, it is with this psychological feature of human thinking that linguists pay close attention to the study of negative connotation (evaluation). On the whole, in the language system, «negative connotative fields are quantitatively more powerful than fields with positive connotations». Positive evaluation occupies a basic place in the word stock [Вольф, 2024; Арутюнова, 1988].

The quantitative ratio analysis of positive and negative anthroponyms shows the result that is contrary to the above statement. It indicates the prevalence of units with the positive evaluation mark. The vocabulary gets enriched at the expense of positive anthroponymic meanings coinciding with the norm that proves the influence of the pragmatic factor on the

language system. The speaker seeks to eliminate, soften unpleasant topics, messages, refrain from naming that has unpleasant connotations, and thus refers to names with positive connotations [Сысоева, 2016: 96-98]. This statement will be presented in more detail.

3.2. This research uses the evaluation classification proposed by S. Khiddekel [Хиддекель, 1983], within which rational, emotional and rational-emotional evaluation types are distinguished.

Rational type of evaluation is based on social experience assessment criteria of native speakers. In linguistics, there are many terms for this type of evaluation: logical evaluation, intellectual-logical evaluation, deontic evaluation. Rational evaluation type is referent-related, i.e. correlates with the referents' world views. The structure of the rational evaluation scale is logically based on the opposition norm – deviations from the norm, in other words, +/– evaluation. The opposition norm – deviations from the norm can be expanded and interpreted with the help of such oppositions: smart – stupid; truthful – untruthful; good – evil, etc. Thus, rational evaluation is associated with the desire to logically justify a certain decision.

Emotional evaluation is based on evaluative experiences, feelings, emotions, i.e. it is focused on the speaker's emotional attitude to the subject of evaluation, for example, hypocoristics *Annie, Mickey, Danny*, reduplicated names *Lulu, Fifi, Vivi / Viva*, names-national symbols expressing national dislike or even hostility *Micky < Michael, Paddy < Patrick* (insulting, derogatory naming forms of the Irish). This type of evaluation is more pragmatically oriented, since emotions determine a speaker's behavior in the process of communication.

Using the approach to the emotional evaluation analysis suggested by V. Shakhovsky [Шаховский, Панченко, 2013], we single out the following types of emotional positive evaluation of anthroponymic units (the examples given belong to the author of the article): 1) affection (most often realized in the names of women and children – *Honey (f), Darlene (f)*) [Hanks & Hodges, 2006]; 2) playfulness (*Winnie (m, f), Piggy (m)* – observational nicknames for a fat person, a child) [Delahunty, 2003]; 3) admiration (*Goldie (f), Pearl (f)* – derived from the names of precious metals and stones); 4) approval (from the appellative anthroponyms *Dexter (m)* – Latin *dexter* ‘right hand’, *Manley (m)* – phonographic association with the adjective *manly* ‘courageous’); 5) playfulness (*Queenie (f)* as a semantic derivative of the name *Victoria*).

Within the framework of the emotional negative evaluation, we single out the following types: 1) condemnation (*Tinker (m)*, originally a nickname – *to tinker* ‘to do something poorly, inaccurately, somehow’); 2) disrespect (*Norris (m)* – norm. *Norreis* ‘north’ disrespectful naming of settlers and inhabitants of the north); 3) resentment (*Jock (m)* is associated with the offensive naming of a Scotsman) [Rybakin, 2000; Delahunty, 2003; Behind the Name; Collins Dictionary and Thesaurus].

The analysis of proper names testifies to the fact that different evaluation types can be associated with emotions – sensory, ethical, aesthetic, etc. In addition, we assume that there is a gap between a wide scale of emotional evaluative meanings (with different shades from affection to humiliation) and lexicographic practice, transforming these meanings into + / – evaluation mark.

Evaluation may be a component of both denotation and connotation in the semantic structure of an anthroponym. In some contexts, the logical perception of evaluative meanings comes to the fore, in others – sensorial perception prevails. The relevant signs of rational-emotional evaluation in anthroponyms are the evaluative meaning of the appellative stem and reference connotations, i.e. extralinguistic features of a name – information about famous bearers, etc. For example, purely linguistic characteristics of the name *Bill* are: a diminutive form of the male name *William* of Germanic origin, the appellative semantics of which is based on the desirable for the Germans formants: *wil* ‘freedom’ + *helm* ‘helmet, protection’ [Behind the name]. A possible reference connotation of the name *Bill* is based on the association with the personality of Bill Gates, wealthy person, computer genius. Consequently, the rational-emotional type of evaluation combines both exclusively linguistic evaluative characteristics of an anthroponym and background knowledge about famous bearers, which enrich the lexical background of the name and give its semantics additional evaluative meanings.

The lexicographic criteria for identifying a mixed type of evaluation are the semantic part of the dictionary entry, which contains the lingual features of the name, and the subject part, containing the label, which traditionally correlates with connotative features. For example, in the dictionary entry of the name *Blanche* (*f*) we find the following: «originally a nickname for a blonde from *blanche*, feminine of Old French *blanc* ‘white’. «It came to be associated with the notion of whiteness as indicating purity» [Hanks & Hodges, 2006]. This connotative attribute makes the name *Blanche* (*f*) correlate with the positive end of the axiological scale. It should be noted that the mixed nature of evaluation can be identified not only with the help of definition, functional-stylistic and emotional-evaluative features. Such labels as ***old fashioned, out of active use as a given name, dated, popular in G.B., USA, Fr.*** can give additional information about the name and shape its axiological characteristics.

Anthroponyms with an evaluative meaning component form a significant layer of the English language system. It seems expedient to consider the evaluative component role in the meaning of anthroponymic units.

3.3. We compiled the corpus taking into account the socio-cultural component of the anthroponymic meaning, which is contained in the subject part of the lexicographic description in accordance with the following criteria for the data selection.

1. Dictionary labels indicating popularity – unpopularity of a name.

This criterion implements the axiological opposition popular – unpopular name, which can be transformed into «+» (popular) / «-» (unpopular) evaluation. Lexical units selected according to this criterion, may be marked in anthroponymic dictionaries by the following labels: *bears perennial popularity after ..., the name has enjoyed steady popularity since the appearance of the novel ..., name popularized by the central character in the novel ..., completely out of fashion after X starred in the film* For example: *Scarlett, Rhett, Ashley* have enjoyed steady popularity since the appearance of the novel «Gone with the Wind» by M. Mitchell [Behind the Name].

2. Markers of a dictionary entry indicating the origin of anthroponymic units.

In this case, the axiological model *native – foreign* is actualized, i.e. opposition of native English names and names of German, French, Norman, Hebrew origin. The lexicographic criteria for determining the origin of anthroponymic units are the vocabulary labels *of Germanic, Greek, French, Norman, Celtic, Old English origin*. In the context of growing globalization, a name is often the only thing that indicates national belonging and emphasizes the national identity.

3. Dictionary indications disclosing appellative stem etymology.

The etymology of the appellative stem of a name is not the main naming motive, since it requires a sufficient amount of cultural and historical knowledge. However, having an etymological reference, one can shape an idea about a name meaning, which might correspond with positive or negative connotations. For example: *Loyal* ‘committed, faithful’, *Felicity* ‘happiness, luck’, *Dotty* ‘weird, strange, senseless’ [Rybakin, 2000].

4. Dictionary labels indicating the geography of a name's popularity.

The anthroponym's belonging to the Irish, Scottish, Welsh national anthroponymic systems may influence the formation of a negative evaluation in the minds of Englishmen, which might be associated with interethnic hostility. In this case, the main classifiers are such dictionary labels as: *preferred by relatives proudly conscious of their Welsh roots ..., name chosen as a token of Scottish national identity ..., a typical Irish name* For example: *Gwendolyn*: a Welsh female first name, derived from Gwendolen; *Africa*: preferred by relatives proudly conscious of their African roots [Behind the Name].

5. Dictionary references to famous name bearers, literary characters, etc. evoking positive or negative associations in the minds of the English. For example: *Richard* may be associated with Richard the Lionheart; *Ebenezer – Ebenezer Scrooge*; *Dwight – Dwight D. Eisenhower*.

4. Data and Generalizations

The component and etymological analysis of the corpus enabled us to provide a set of semantic features. The basic elements of the lexical background of the units studied are: the

etymology of the appellative stem and cultural-historical component (extralinguistic encyclopedic information about a name).

4.1. The evaluation mark is defined with the reference to a positive or negative attitude of a linguistic persona to the reality aspects explicated by anthroponyms. Table 1 contains the ratio of the units studied.

Table 1. *Types of evaluation explicators (quantitative characteristics)*

Evaluation explicators	Quantity	%
Appellative stem etymology	1670	51
Cultural-historical component	1605	49
<i>Total</i>	<i>3275</i>	<i>100</i>

The above data show that both types are almost equal. This result is in keeping with the famous onomastic theory as for the coexistence of linguistic and extralinguistic elements of information in proper names' semantics. For instance, the etymology of the female name *Merry* correlates with the vocabulary word *merry* having a positive connotation, thus the name is marked with «+» evaluation. The cultural-historical component of the male anthroponym *Clint* (a short form of *Clinton*) might be explicated through the association with a talented American, director, producer, etc. Clint Eastwood, the popularity and positive evaluation being sustained by the dictionary entry: 'now the name is bestowed because of its association with a popular American film actor, director, producer, composer and politician' [Behind the Name].

4.2. On the basis of conceptual features, the following semantic classes of the evaluative anthroponyms have been singled out (see Table 2):

Table 2. *Semantic classes of English evaluative anthroponyms*

#	Semantic classes	Quantity	%	Examples
1.	Allusive EA	1294	39,5	<i>Narcissus (m)</i> – name of the Greek mythology character falling in love with his own reflection, the embodiment of self-admiration; <i>Cordelia (f)</i> – heroine of Shakespeare's <i>The Tragedy of King Lear</i> , king's youngest and beloved daughter;
2.	EA with the seme <i>appearance</i>	685	20,7	<i>Goldie (f)</i> – name indicates beautiful goldish hair colour; <i>Bella, Belle (f)</i> – name associated with the Italian adjective <i>bella</i> or French <i>belle</i> 'beautiful';
3.	EA indicating <i>occupation</i> and <i>social status</i>	379	11,5	<i>Skipper (f)</i> – originates from the nickname <i>skipper</i> 'captain, commander'; <i>Earl (m)</i> – name was given to those who worked for earls to ironically stress low social status of a name bearer;
4.	EA of the sphere <i>religion</i>	265	8,1	<i>Faith (f), Felicity (f)</i> – Puritan anthroponyms, unpopular as given names;

Table 2 (continued)

5.	EA describing <i>character traits</i>	164	5,3	<i>Loyal (m); Curtis (m)</i> – stems from the French <i>curteis</i> or English <i>courteous</i> ‘polite’;
6.	EA with the seme <i>cultural intolerance</i>	132	4	<i>Norris (m)</i> – Norman <i>norreis</i> ‘North’, obtains negative evaluation due to unfriendly relationships between northerners and southerners; <i>Scot (m)</i> – name popular in Scotland;
7.	EA with the seme <i>interpersonal relationships</i>	116	3,6	<i>Honey (f); Pet (f)</i> – (derived from <i>Petula</i>);
8.	Others	237	7,3	<i>Donna (f)</i> – Italian <i>donna</i> ‘lady’; <i>Holly (f)</i> – <i>holly</i> is the plant associated with European Christmas
	Total	3275	100	

The data in Table 2 reveals the asymmetry in corpus behavior. The most productive semantic group is «Allusive evaluative anthroponyms» amounting 1294 units (39,5%). Allusiveness of proper names results from the identity of the name either with a famous bearer’s personality or with a particular situation. Such names are widely popular far beyond the linguacultural areas. Internationally acclaimed names often acquire a symbolic character [Алефиренко, 2020]. The units entering the biggest class have been further classified into three groups: 1) historical allusive EA: *Rockefeller* – John D. Rockefeller, American industrialist and philanthropist – wealth, beneficence; 2) literature allusive EA: *Simon Legree* – fictional character, the principal villain in Harriet Beecher Stowe’s antislavery novel *Uncle Tom’s Cabin* – cruel, relentless person; 3) Bible allusive EA: *Dorcas* – the name of the Christian woman in the «New Testament» who sewed clothes and distributed them to the poor – philanthropist.

The group «Evaluative anthroponyms with the seme *appearance* rank second» (685 units, 20,7%). Semantically the units of this group are not homogeneous. The four subgroups were singled out: 1) colour of hair, skin and eyes: *Ginger (f), Silver (f), Hazel (f)*; 2) bodily constitution: *Piggy, Billy*; 3) fashion style: *Buck (m), Buster (m), Dandy (m)*; 4) facial features: *Taliesin (m)* Gaelic *tal* ‘eyebrows’ + *iesin* ‘beautiful’, *Courtney (m, f)* Old French *court* + *nez* ‘snub nose’ [Hanks & Hodges, 2006, Behind the Name].

The classes «Evaluative anthroponyms indicating *occupation* and *social status*» (379 units, 11,5%), «Evaluative anthroponyms of the sphere *religion*» (265 units, 8,1%), «Evaluative anthroponyms describing *character traits*» (164, 5,3%) are less numerous. The semantic class «Evaluative anthroponyms with the seme *cultural intolerance*» (116 units, 3,6%) is the least productive one. The group «Others» was singled out holding together 237 EA, whose semantics does not correlate with the above semantic classes.

5.3. The semantic analysis of the units under study reveals the specific evaluation nature in the subsystem of anthroponymic vocabulary. Unlike evaluative common nouns, characterized by the predominance of negatively colored lexemes, positively colored units prevail in the corpus. The analysis of the axiological characteristics of English anthroponyms testifies to the significant prevalence of positively evaluative units over negatively evaluative ones (see Table 3).

Table 3. *Ratio of positively and negatively colored anthroponyms*

Axiological characteristics	Quantity	%
«+» evaluation	2639	80,6
«-» evaluation	636	19,4
<i>Total</i>	3275	100

Positive evaluation anthroponyms considerably prevail in the English anthroponymic system. Containing only positive aspects of reality in their semantics, they reflect specific features of the conceptual world views of the English cultural and linguistic community in general and naming motivation in particular. The naming motivation is governed by the desire of naming participants to choose a name with positive semantics or positive cultural and historical background.

5. Conclusion

5.1. The linguacultural study of the English evaluative anthroponymicon reveals the peculiarities of speakers' worldview, which are reflected in the form of mental models and are fixed in the onomastic picture of the world.

5.2. The evaluation in anthroponymic semantics is actualized by: the stem etymology and cultural-historical component.

5.3. The ratio of positively and negatively marked anthroponyms indicates a significant dominance of the former. Anthroponyms with «+» evaluation prevail within all semantic classes. The most significant predominance of «+» over «-» anthroponyms is found within the semantic class «Allusive evaluative anthroponyms». The semantic class «Evaluative anthroponyms with the seme *interpersonal relationships*» is represented by anthroponyms with purely positive evaluation, since most of such names originate from affectionate forms of addressing a person.

5.4. Evaluation in semantic structure of anthroponyms can combine with other connotation components. The combination of evaluative and cultural-historic meaning components is mostly attributed to the allusive anthroponyms. Evaluation interacts with the emotive connotation component in EA with the seme *interpersonal relationships*. Evaluation being sustained by expressive and stylistic connotation components, is detected in literature, biblical EA, EA indicating occupation and social status and cultural intolerance.

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